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Research Article

**FORMULATION DEVELOPMENT AND INVITRO
EVALUATION OF SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS
OF RISPERIDONE BY USING NATURAL POLYMERS****C. Thanusha, J.Bharathi**

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Abstract:

The present work studied the natural polymer based once a day matrix tablet of Risperidone. From the wide range of hydrophilic polymers, *k*-carrageenan, λ -carrageenan and locust bean gum. Combinations of the two different gums *k*-carrageenan and locust bean gum and λ -carrageenan and locust bean gum were formulated in different ratios 20:80, 40:60, 50:50, 60:40 and 80:20 to exploit rheological synergism between two gums. Further the formulations were prepared from the formulation which exhibited maximum retardation such that each contains 10% less polymer concentration than the previous formulation in order to achieve the once-a-day matrix tablet of Risperidone containing least amount of polymer. The blends were prepared by non-aqueous wet granulation techniques with lactose as a diluent in formulations. The dried blends were compressed with other necessary excipients. The tablets were evaluated for hardness, thickness, drug content uniformity, in-vitro drug release studies for 24 hours (USP dissolution apparatus II, phosphate buffer-pH 6.8, 50 rpm, $37\pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$), water uptake studies, swelling studies and in of the matrix tablet. The amount of Risperidone released from the tablet formulations was estimated at 210nm using a UV spectrophotometer. The kinetic analysis of selected formulations were performed and found to follow Korsmeyer-Peppas model through non-fickian transport mechanism. The following conclusions can be drawn from the above study. From the results obtained we can conclude that the polymers selected for the study, can be used individually for the sustained drug delivery of Risperidone locust bean gum was used in combination with *k*-carrageenan and λ -carrageenan in 60:40 and 20:80 ratios respectively with least in vitro drug release and can be used to reduce the concentration of polymer from the tablet. 30% polymer reduction in case of *k*-carrageenan and locust bean gum and 20% with λ -carrageenan and locust bean gum combination was achieved.

Key words: Formulation Development, Invitro Evaluation, Sustained Release Matrix Tablets, Risperidone, Natural Polymers

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INTRODUCTION:

Natural polymers are polymers that break down in a normal and biocompatible way and lose their individuality when they come into contact with biological components.¹ These polymers are chosen over semi-synthetic and synthetic excipients. Bacterial growth, lot to lot variation, unpredictable ratio of hydration, and lower thickness during preservation are all issues that need to be addressed. Incorrect mechanical characteristics and low strength.² Chemical adjustments were performed to improve the stability and process ability of newly discovered gums. If the newly created gums are biodegradable and biocompatible, they can be employed; if not, a biodegradable component can be added to make them biodegradable.³ To alter of molecular interaction between polymers, a variety of techniques can be applied. There are two approaches to choose from: physical and chemical.⁴ Physical technique Dry heat, water-logged steam, microwave, UV, even gamma radiation can all be utilized to generate a molecular interaction between polymers.⁵ Polymers are treated with chemicals such aldehydes, epichlorohydrin, borax, or glutaraldehyde in the chemical approach. Temperature cross-linking is single of the greatest advantageous cross-linking operations as it eliminates the need for harsh organic chemicals in large-scale production, as well as the associated equipment and methods.⁶ Because of the increased dose flexibility for design, the oral route of delivery for sustained release systems had gained considerable attention. The type of delivery system, the ailment being handled, the patient, the duration of medication, and the drug quality are all significant considerations in the design of oral sustained release delivery systems.⁷ The major goal of therapy is to keep the amount of drug in the blood at a steady level for a longer time. A major component of reaching this goal is the establishment of appropriate dose regimens. Sustained-release dosage forms are a type of drug administration that releases medication continuously over time to give long-term therapeutic benefit. Dosage is given in a single dose.⁸

For treating diabetes, it has been considered important that both a post prandial blood glucose level and a fasting blood glucose level are decreased to make them to normal levels. Other antidiabetics are primarily used for decreasing either a post prandial blood glucose level or a fasting blood glucose level to make it close to a normal level, but Risperidone has been used to control both post prandial blood glucose level as well as a fasting blood glucose level. Risperidone is a BCS class II (Insoluble, highly permeable) drug. The plasma half life of Risperidone is 1.5h. The usual oral dosage regimen is 60—180mg taken 3 times a day for Risperidone immediate release tablets. The Risperidone controlled or sustained release formulation would be more useful than the Risperidone immediate release tablets from the view point of avoidance of side effect, or of easy control of both PBG and FBG to enable control of both PBG and FBG for moderate and severe diabetes patients. Thus, there is a need to formulate oral sustained drug delivery system of Risperidone.

The oral sustained release drug delivery system of Risperidone can be formulated using various synthetic as well as natural hydrophilic polymers. The biodegradable nature and easy availability of the natural polymers makes them suitable for using as a sustained release polymer. The natural polymers also exhibit a rheological synergism between them when two polymers are mixed together. By using this property of the natural polymers can be used to reduce the total polymer concentration from the sustained release matrix tablet and once a day formulation of the Risperidone can be formulated containing least amount of polymer.

Risperidone[N-(trans-4-isopropylcyclohexylcarbonyl)-D-phenylalanine] is a novel mealtime glucose regulator approved for the treatment of type II diabetes mellitus. Risperidone has a rapid onset and short duration of insulinotropic action that results in reduction of mealtime glucose rise and lowers the postabsorptive potential for hypoglycemia in humans and experimental animals.

MATERIALS AND INSTRUMENTS:**Materials used****Table.No.1 : Materials used**

S. No.	Chemical and reagents	Suppliers
1	Risperidone	Glenmark pharmaceuticals ltd.
2	K- Carrageenan	Otto kemi Pvt. ltd.
3	λ - Carrageenan	Lucid Colloids ltd.
4	Locust bean gum	Research lab – fine chem ltd.
5	Colloidal silicon dioxide	Dekkan Pharmaceuticals ltd.

PREFORMULATION

Preformulation testing is an investigation of physical and chemical properties of a drug substance alone and when combined with excipients. It is the first step in the rational development of dosage forms.

Preformulation studies relate to pharmaceutical and analytical investigation carried out in supporting formulation development efforts of the dosage forms.

UV SPECTROSCOPIC METHOD FOR ANALYSIS OF Risperidone**A. UV spectroscopy: (Determination of λ_{max})**

Risperidone was accurately weighed and dissolved in the solvent (Phosphate buffer 6.8) to obtain solution of 100 μ g/ml. UV spectrum was run from 200-400nm and λ_{max} was recorded using UV spectrophotometer.

Preparation of calibration curve of Risperidone

Risperidone solution of 100 μ g/ml was prepared in

phosphate buffer pH 6.8 and UV spectrum was recorded in the wavelength range from 200-400 nm.

Standard stock solution: 100 mg of Risperidone was accurately weighed and transferred to 100ml volumetric flask and dissolved in phosphate buffer pH 6.8 to get solution of concentration 1000 μ g/ml and this solution was further diluted suitably to get solution of concentration 50 μ g/ml.

Working stock solution: A series of Risperidone solutions ranging from 5 to 30 μ g/ml was prepared from standard stock solution in phosphate buffer pH 6.8. The absorbance of all solutions was measured against phosphate buffer pH 6.8 as blank at 210 nm using UV spectrophotometer. Beer's law was obeyed in the concentration range of 5-30 μ g/ml. The high values of regression coefficient (0.9992) estimated the linearity of relationship between concentration and absorbance.

Table.No. 2: Calibration curve for Risperidone

S.No.	Concentration(μ g/ml)	Absorbance (nm)
1	0	0
2	5	0.145
3	10	0.297
4	15	0.459
5	20	0.591
6	25	0.729
7	30	0.873
Slope	0.0294	
R^2	0.9992	

Fig.No.1: Calibration curve of Risperidone in phosphate buffer pH 6.8

FORMULATIONS OF SUSTAINED RELEASE MATRIX TABLETS OF RISPERIDONE

Preparation of hydrophilic matrix tablets

A. Study of various gums and its different concentration levels

The natural gums like k – carrageenan, λ - carrageenan and locust bean gum were selected for the preparation of tablets and their concentrations in the formulations ranging from different ratios were used.

B. Procedure for preparation of matrix tablet:

- Accurately weighed quantity of drug (Risperidone) and polymer were passed through 40# sieve.
- The polymer and the drug were then mixed in a mortar by geometric progression for a period of 10-15 minutes.
- This mixture was then granulated with isopropyl alcohol, and sieved using 18# sieve. Obtained granules were then dried in hot air oven at 40°C for 10-15 minutes.
- The dried granules were mixed with magnesium stearate and colloidal silicon dioxide and lactose monohydrate for further 2 minutes and compressed under 10mm std. concave punch.

K – carrageenan

Table No.3: Composition of k - carrageenan based matrix tablets of Risperidone

Ingredients	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃
Risperidone	120	120	120
K - carrageenan	90	105	120
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	78	63	48
PVP K – 30	6	6	6

*All the quantities are in mg

λ - carrageenan**Table No.4: Composition of λ - carrageenan based matrix tablets of Risperidone**

Ingredients	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆
Risperidone	120	120	120
λ - carrageenan	90	105	120
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	78	63	48
PVP K – 30	6	6	6

*All the quantities are in mg

Locust bean gum**Table No.5: Composition of locust bean gum based matrix tablets of Risperidone**

Ingredients	F ₇	F ₈	F ₉
Risperidone	120	120	120
Locust bean gum	90	105	120
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	78	63	48
PVP K – 30	6	6	6

*All the quantities are in mg

K – carrageenan + Locust bean gum**A. K – carrageenan + Locust bean gum combinations**

From the results obtained by previous studies carried out using individual k – carrageenan (F₁ – F₃) and locust bean gum as hydrophilic matrix (F₇ – F₉), the percentage in which the k - carrageenan and locust bean gum combination could be used to formulate once day formulation of Risperidone was selected. These ratios are in percentages of dry polymer weight i.e. 20% of k – carrageenan and 80% of locust bean gum in F₁₀ and likewise for other ratios.

Table No.6: Composition of k - carrageenan + locust bean gum combinations based matrix tablet of Risperidone

Ingredients	F ₁₀ (20:80)	F ₁₁ (40:60)	F ₁₂ (50:50)	F ₁₃ (60:40)	F ₁₄ (80:20)
Risperidone	120	120	120	120	120
K – carrageenan	24	48	60	72	96
Locust bean gum	96	72	60	48	24
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	48	48	48	48	48
PVP K - 30	6	6	6	6	6

*All the quantities are in mg

K - carrageenan + Locust bean gum 40:60 combinations

From the results obtained in above study, 40:60 ratio of k – carrageenan: locust bean gum in F₄₁ was chosen to reduce the total polymer concentration from the tablet. Now, formulations were formulated such that each formulation contains 12mg less polymer content than previous formulation. It means from F₄₅ to F₄₉, there is 10% less polymer concentration in each formulation i.e. F₄₆ contains 12mg less polymer content than F₄₅ and so on, to obtain the formulation giving once a day formulation of Risperidone containing least amount of polymer.

Table No.7: Composition of k – carrageenan + locust bean gum 40:60 combinations based matrix tablets of Risperidone

Ingredients	F15	F16	F17	F18	F19
Risperidone	120	120	120	120	120
K - carrageenan	21.6	19.2	16.8	14.4	12
Locust bean gum	86.4	76.8	67.2	57.6	48
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	60	72	84	96	108
PVP K - 30	6	6	6	6	6

*All the quantities are in mg

λ – carrageenan + Locust bean gum**A. λ – carrageenan + Locust bean gum combinations**

From the results obtained by previous studies carried out using individual λ - carrageenan (F₄ – F₆) and locust bean gum as hydrophilic matrix (F₇ – F₉), the percentage in which the λ – carrageenan and locust bean gum combination could be used to formulate once a day formulation of Risperidone was selected. The proportions of gums selected were 20:80, 40:60, 50:50, 60:40, 80:20 as mentioned in the table no. 13. These ratios are in percentages of dry polymer weight i.e. 20% of λ – carrageenan and 80% of locust bean gum in F₂₀ and likewise for other ratios.

Table No.8: Composition of λ - carrageenan + locust bean gum combinations-based matrix tablets of Risperidone

Ingredients	F ₂₀ (20:80)	F ₂₁ (40:60)	F ₂₂ (50:50)	F ₂₃ (60:40)	F ₂₄ (80:20)
Risperidone	120	120	120	120	120
λ – carrageenan	24	48	60	72	96
Locust bean gum	96	72	60	48	24
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	48	48	48	48	48
PVP K – 30	6	6	6	6	6

B. λ – carrageenan + Locust bean gum 20:80 combinations

From the results obtained in above study, 20:80 ratio of λ – carrageenan: locust bean gum in F₂₀ was chosen to reduce the total polymer concentration from the tablet. Now, formulations were formulated such that each formulation contains 12mg less polymer content than previous formulation. It means from F₂₅ to F₂₇, there is 10% less polymer concentration in each formulation i.e. F₂₆ contains 12mg less polymer content than F₂₅ and so on, to obtain the formulation giving once a day formulation of Risperidone containing least amount of polymer.

Table No.9: Composition of λ – carrageenan + locust bean gum 20:80 combinations based matrix tablets

of Risperidone

Ingredients	F25	F26	F27
Risperidone	120	120	120
λ – carrageenan	21.6	19.2	16.8
Locust bean gum	86.4	76.8	67.2
Colloidal silicon dioxide	3	3	3
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3
Lactose monohydrate	60	72	84
PVP K – 30	6	6	6

*All the quantities are in mg

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS:**PRE-FORMULATION STUDIES****Organoleptic properties**

These tests were performed as procedure given, Preformulation part. The results are illustrated in following table.

Table 10. Organoleptic properties

Test	Specifications/limits	Observations
Color	White, Crystalline powder	White, Crystalline powder
Odour	Odorless, Bitter taste	Odorless, Bitter taste

The results complies as per specifications

Angle of repose

It was determined as per procedure preformulation in material and method part.

The results are illustrated in following table.

Table 11. Flow properties

Material	Angle of repose
Risperidone	27 $\square$.14"

The result shows that drug having poor flow

Bulk density and tapped density.

It was determined as per procedure given preformulation in material and method part. The results are illustrated in table.

Table 12. Density

Materials	Bulk Density(gm/ml)	Tapped density(gm/ml)
Risperidone	0.19	0.26

Powder compressibility

It was determined as per procedure given in preformulation in material and method part. The results are illustrated in table.

Table 13. Powder compressibility

Material	Compressibility index	Hausner ratio
Risperidone	31.42%	1.18

The results shows that drug having poor flow property

Melting point

It was determined as per procedure given in preformulation in material and method part. The results are illustrated in following table.

Table 14. Melting point

Material	Material point range	result
Risperidone	137 °C	Complies

The result complies as per specification.

SOLUTION PROPERTIES

pH of the solution

It was determined as per procedure given in preformulation in material and method part. The results are illustrated in following table.

Table 15. pH

Material	Test	Specification	Observation
Risperidone	pH	6.5	6.5

The result complies as per specification

Solubility

It was determined as per procedure given in preformulation in material and method part. The results are illustrated in following table.

Table 16. Solubility

Test	Specification	Result
solubility	soluble in methanol, ethanol, chloroform, dissolved in acetone, ethyl ether, almost insoluble in water.	Complies

The result complies as per specification.

Table.No.17: Band Assignments for the Infrared Absorption Spectrum of Risperidone

Band Energy (cm-1)	Assignment
1280 - 1431	carboxyl, carboxylate
1651	carbonyl
2866 - 3047	C-H stretching
1714	C=O
3298	N-H stretching
1296	C-O stretching
1446	C-O-H stretching
3296 - 3311	N-H stretching

it was observed that there were no changes in these main peaks in IR spectra of mixture of drug and polymers, which show there were no physical interactions because of some bond formation between drug and polymer.

PRECOMPRESSION STUDIES:

EVALUATION OF RISPERIDONE TABLETS:

Table. No: 18. WEIGHT VARIATION AND FRIABILITY:

Batch. No	Weight Variation (%)	Friability (%)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)
F1	301±1.52	0.21	4.12±0.2	8.07
F2	304±2.37	0.23	4.03±0.2	7.92
F3	298±1.44	0.33	4.22±0.1	8.14
F4	320±1.86	0.42	4.31±0.1	7.54
F5	312±2.56	0.41	4.07±0.1	7.92
F6	303±2.13	0.23	4.12±0.1	7.61
F7	304±1.52	0.24	4.06±0.2	7.47
F8	318±1.49	0.20	4.19±0.3	7.42
F9	290±2.37	0.18	4.38±0.2	8.10
F10	312±1.91	0.25	4.12±0.1	8.32
F11	309±1.34	0.24	4.16±0.2	8.23
F12	317±2.03	0.35	4.14±0.2	8.14
F13	309±1.92	0.27	4.23±0.2	7.76
F14	303±1.66	0.52	4.08±0.1	7.91

Table. No: 19. WEIGHT VARIATION, FRIABILITY THICKNESS & HARDNESS

Batch. No	Weight Variation (%)	Friability (%)	Thickness (mm)	Hardness (Kg/cm ²)
F15	320±2.12	0.16	4.01±0.1	8.09
F16	309±1.03	0.34	4.03±0.1	8.32
F17	314±1.47	0.31	4.12±0.2	8.14
F18	306±1.42	0.24	4.62±0.3	8.45
F19	313±2.03	0.23	4.03±0.1	8.15
F20	312±1.74	0.29	4.08±0.2	7.92
F21	303±1.92	0.41	4.31±0.2	7.65
F22	291±2.04	0.36	4.26±0.1	8.19
F23	289±1.92	0.24	4.12±0.3	8.74
F24	301±1.25	0.31	4.14±0.2	8.31
F25	316±1.36	0.17	4.19±0.2	8.47
F26	303±1.23	0.24	4.27±0.1	8.23
F27	301±1.82	0.29	4.21±0.1	8.35

Discussion:

The weight variation of the tablet in the range of $\pm 1.03\%$ to $\pm 2.37\%$ (below 5%) complying with pharmacopoeial specification.

The friability of the tablet in the range of 0.16 % to 0.52% (below 1%) complying with pharmacopoeial specifications. The thickness of the formulations from F1- F12 was found to be in the range of 4.01 ± 0.1 to 4.31 ± 0.2 and hardness of the formulated tablets was found to 7.42 to 8.74 indicating a satisfactory mechanical strength for the sustained release.

Table.No.20. In vitro drug release profile of F₁₀ – F₁₄

Time (hours)	BATCH NO.				
	F10	F11	F12	F13	F14
1	6.24	05.93	09.62	10.47	8.21
2	10.41	09.14	14.27	16.21	17.43
4	16.70	13.42	19.43	23.83	24.71
6	21.51	19.74	24.17	29.72	31.84
8	26.07	24.34	29.82	36.14	39.81
10	30.74	29.91	35.07	41.57	45.77
12	36.14	33.40	40.33	47.13	52.86
14	41.29	39.72	48.64	54.71	61.28
16	46.30	45.81	54.73	60.43	69.56
18	50.47	51.34	60.81	69.57	76.25
20	58.67	56.17	69.40	73.14	83.17
22	65.12	62.55	74.21	81.57	90.74
24	71.45	68.88	80.75	88.15	95.87

Table.No. 21. In vitro drug release profile of F₁₅ – F₁₉

Time (hours)	BATCH NO.				
	F15	F16	F17	F18	F19
1	05.31	09.17	10.71	12.42	16.88
2	11.78	14.24	19.22	20.71	25.40
4	19.26	20.14	27.34	27.48	32.46
6	25.87	29.14	34.19	33.85	44.58
8	31.74	36.72	40.28	40.24	52.86
10	39.45	41.34	48.17	49.33	60.44
12	44.67	47.60	55.83	56.81	69.14
14	50.41	54.12	61.24	64.27	74.65
16	58.62	60.71	69.17	75.08	80.19
18	63.77	69.48	76.57	83.72	86.17
20	69.12	74.52	85.14	91.47	92.12
22	73.20	80.12	92.12	99.21	101.83
24	79.51	88.44	98.90		

Table.No. 22. In vitro drug release profile of F₂₀ – F₂₄

Time (hours)	BATCH NO.				
	F20	F21	F22	F23	F24
1	11.78	13.37	12.44	16.41	19.74
2	18.35	19.12	18.75	22.77	29.45
4	24.89	26.22	24.22	30.22	36.88
6	29.08	33.64	30.95	39.72	43.95
8	34.24	38.09	36.74	45.21	51.93
10	39.96	44.78	42.33	51.17	59.48
12	44.47	49.08	50.87	59.84	66.85
14	50.78	53.57	59.24	66.30	74.24
16	57.20	59.74	65.85	74.81	81.75
18	62.28	65.51	71.39	80.17	92.24
20	69.14	71.92	78.09	92.28	101.63
22	71.45	77.69	84.33	99.61	
24	77.68	83.65	90.40		

Table.No. 23. In vitro drug release profile of F₂₅ – F₂₇

Time (hours)	BATCH NO.		
	F25	F26	F27
1	08.31	10.47	16.48
2	13.45	16.17	22.64
4	19.97	21.08	30.47
6	24.63	26.65	39.38
8	30.24	39.14	47.08
10	38.22	48.92	54.22
12	42.38	54.67	61.84
14	50.52	61.07	69.22
16	59.22	69.24	76.54
18	68.54	76.72	81.26
20	74.91	84.24	87.92
22	81.65	91.02	94.24
24	88.05	97.75	102.35

Drug Release Kinetics

The release of Risperidone from the matrices was evaluated by using PCP Disso V3 .To evaluate the drug release kinetics, formulations showing a significant slow release were chosen. In general, the

mechanism of drug release from polymeric matrices can be described by the swelling phenomenon. The solvent molecules move inside the polymeric matrix like a “front”, simultaneously, the thickness of the area increases with time in the opposite direction. The mechanism of drug release can be described by a

second phenomenon that involves the disentanglement and erosion of the polymer. By using the Korsmeyer and Peppas model equation, the n values were obtained between 0.65 and 0.97 for all formulations. These values are characteristic of anomalous kinetics (non Fickian) suggesting that more than one mechanism might be involved in the release kinetics. Here, the polymer relaxation and erosion are the rate-controlling steps. When $n = 0.5$, Fickian diffusion is the rate-controlling step (case I transport). Values of n between 0.5 and 1 indicate the contribution of both the diffusion process as well as polymer relaxation in controlling the release kinetics (non-Fickian, anomalous or first- order release). When the exponent n takes a value of 1.0, the drug release rate is independent of time. This case corresponds to zero-order release kinetics (also termed as case II transport). It should be noted that the two extreme values of $n =$

0.5 and 1 are only valid for slab geometry. For cylindrical tablets, these values range from $0.45 < n <$

0.89 for Fickian, Anomalous or Case II transport respectively. The Peppas model gave a good fit to most of the dissolution data of the swellable matrix tablets as shown by the R^2 values ($0.9892 < R^2 < 0.9968$). For all the Risperidone matrix formulations, the contribution of polymer relaxation occurs throughout the entire dissolution period. This was also apparent from the n values obtained for selected formulations, which approach anomalous transport. In general, the relaxational contribution was higher for the formulations with higher n values. The k - carrageenan formulation (F₃) showed the highest contribution of polymer relaxation.

Table.No:24. Drug release parameters for selected formulations

Formulation	n values	R ²	k values	Best fit model
F13	0.9748	0.9897	4.2354	Peppas
F16	0.9448	0.9897	4.2416	Peppas
F19	0.7997	0.9935	4.1579	Peppas
F17	0.8026	0.9968	4.1625	Peppas
F26	0.7458	0.9914	4.1145	Peppas

The regression coefficient values and n values show that the drug releases follow Non - Fickian release (Diffusion and swelling).

SUMMARY

Risperidone is a BCS class II (Insoluble, highly permeable) drug. The plasma half life of Risperidone is 1.5h and bioavailability of 73%. The usual oral dosage regimen is 60— 180mg taken 3 times a day for Risperidone immediate release tablets. The controlled or sustained release formulation of Risperidone would be more useful than the Risperidone immediate release tablets from the view point of avoidance of side effect, improvement of compliance to patients and to enable control of both post prandial blood glucose level and fasting blood glucose level for moderate and severe diabetes patients. Hence, an attempt was made to develop a sustained-release (SR) oral dosage form of Risperidone instead of IR tablet.

The present work studied the natural polymer based once a day matrix tablet of Risperidone. From the wide range of hydrophilic polymers, k - carrageenan, λ - carrageenan and locust bean gum. Combinations of the two different gums k - carrageenan and locust bean gum and λ -carrageenan and locust bean gum were formulated in different ratios 20:80, 40:60, 50:50, 60:40 and 80:20 to exploit rheological synergism between two gums. Further the formulations were

prepared from the formulation which exhibited maximum retardation such that each contains 10% less polymer concentration than the previous formulation in order to achieve the once a day matrix tablet of Risperidone containing least amount of polymer. The blends were prepared by non-aqueous wet granulation techniques with lactose as a diluent in formulations. The dried blends were compressed with other necessary excipients. The tablets were evaluated for hardness, thickness, drug content uniformity, in-vitro drug release studies for 24 hours (USP dissolution apparatus II, phosphate buffer-pH 6.8, 50 rpm, $37 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$), water uptake studies, swelling studies and in of the matrix tablet. The amount of Risperidone released from the tablet formulations was estimated at 210nm using a UV spectrophotometer. The kinetic analysis of selected formulations were performed and found to follow Korsmeyer-Peppas model through non-fickian transport mechanism.

The following conclusions can be drawn from the above study.

From the results obtained we can conclude that the polymers selected for the study, can be used individually for the sustained drug delivery of

Risperidone locust bean gum was used in combination with k-carrageenan and λ -carrageenan in 60:40 and 20:80 ratios respectively with least in vitro drug release and can be used to reduce the concentration of polymer from the tablet. 30% polymer reduction in case of k-carrageenan and locust bean gum and 20% with λ -carrageenan and locust bean gum combination was achieved.

CONCLUSION:

Once a day sustained release matrix tablets of Risperidone was prepared by using natural polymers k-carrageenan, λ -carrageenan and locust bean gum. Natural polymers were selected due to their easy availability and cheaper in cost and we can get standard uniformity and combinations of two different gums carrageenan and locust bean gum were formulated in different ratios to exploit the rheological synergism between two gums in order to achieve once a day matrix tablets of Risperidone further formulations were prepared from the formulations exhibited maximum retardation the controlled or sustained release formulations of Risperidone would be more useful than the Risperidone immediate release tablets from the new point of side effects improvement of compliance to patients and to enable to control of both post prandial blood glucose level and fasting blood glucose level for moderate and severe diabetes patients.

Hence an attempt was made to develop a sustained release oral dosage form of Risperidone instead of immediate release tablet.

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